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Beyond Barbed Boundaries: Analysing *Veer-Zaara* as an Alternative Border Narrative

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***Abstract:** The India-Pakistan border is a matter of nationalistic tensions for long with historical trauma. While mainstream discourse perpetuates an antagonistic border narrative, Bollywood cinemas, on the other hand, often offer an alternative lens of cultural proximity and human connections. *Veer-Zaara* (2004), directed by Yash Chopra, is one of those films which offers a counter-hegemonic representation of the border. It reimagines the border not as a site of division but as a bridge of shared cultural memory. Thus, this study explores how *Veer-Zaara* constructs a transgressive border narrative by employing spatial representation or gender dynamics and emotional subversion of state-centric nationalism. Employing Benedict Anderson's concept of "Imagined Communities" and other theories on nationalism and postcolonial film studies, the paper will examine how the film deconstructs the rigid self vs. other binary between India and Pakistan. Unlike previous Bollywood war films that reinforce national boundaries, *Veer-Zaara* integrates Sufi and Sikh spiritual motifs, musical symbolism, and romantic transcendence to promote a people-centric reconciliation. The study argues that the film's alternative border discourse aligns with peace-building efforts, challenging state-driven narratives by foregrounding*

humanistic and affective ties over geopolitical hostilities. Ultimately, Veer-Zaara represents the potential of cinema as a cultural text to renegotiate national identities and offer a vision of cross-border solidarity.

Keywords: Border Narratives, Bollywood Cinema, India-Pakistan Relations, Nationalism, Boundaries

“Borders are not only tangible physical features located at the edge of state territory but are also cogent conceptual abstractions.” (36)

(Shubhi Misra “Border and Bordering Practices from the Cinematic Lens.”)

Introduction:

The relationship between India and Pakistan has long been marked by tension, political rivalry, and deep-rooted historical trauma since the Partition of 1947. The border between these two nations has long been a matter of conflict, both physically and ideologically, influencing the socio-political and cultural landscapes of South Asia. The highly militarised India-Pakistan border has not only been a demarcation of territorial sovereignty but has also shaped national narratives and identities. Cinema has played an important role in reflecting as well as subverting these national discourses. As Gita Viswanath and Salma Malik rightly stated, “Cinema is one of the most popular and influential cultural productions in the lives of people in India and Pakistan.” (61) Traditional Bollywood movies often stick to nationalistic themes that emphasise the dichotomy of “self” and “other.” Conversely, the emergence of alternative cinematic narratives offers a clearer view of the border, which transcends geopolitical and ideological

boundaries. Bollywood has the ability to humanise the intricacies of cross-border relations, which presents a chance to (re)imagine contentious borders as spaces of cultural affinity and human solidarity.

Yash Chopra directed the film *Veer-Zaara* (2004), which is a notable example of an alternative border narrative which subverts traditional notions of conflict. The film tells the tragic love story of an ill-fated Indian male and a Pakistani female. Their relationship is torn apart by personal struggles and political divisions. The film portrays the deep cultural and emotional bonds shared between India and Pakistan. This paper is a modest attempt to explore *Veer-Zaara* as a predominant nationalistic rhetoric of the India-Pakistan border. The film shows a border which is not demarcated by division but by the possibility of human connection. The study is substantial in contributing to film studies and border studies. The film (re)imagines the border as a site of convergence rather than conflict. The study incorporates Benedict Anderson's concept of "imagined communities" along with Edensor's ideas of national spatialization and other postcolonial film studies. This study probes deeper into the film *Veer-Zaara* to explore how it challenges the rigid binary of "self" and "other" through its emotional and spiritual depth. As we see, much of the existing scholarship on Bollywood and conflict focuses on its depiction of war and nationalism. Whereas *Veer-Zaara* provides a counter-narrative that foregrounds cultural affinity and the possibility of cross-border solidarity. Thus, the research tries to fill the gap by analysing this alternative 'cine-narrative' to understand the role of Bollywood in (re)shaping perspectives on national boundaries and its potential contribution to peace-building in the context of India-Pakistan relations.

Theoretical Framework & Literature Review

Cinema has long been a powerful medium in shaping national identity and reinforcing political ideologies. Given the long-standing tensions between India and Pakistan, Bollywood often plays a dual role—promoting national pride while also offering moments of cultural connection and understanding. The concept of nationalism, as theorised by Ernest Gellner and John Breuilly, underscores the role of cultural production in shaping a collective identity (Gellner 53-62; Breuilly 18-42). Benedict Anderson’s seminal work *Imagined Communities* (1983) extends this argument, proposing that nations are “imagined” through shared symbols, narratives, and cultural expressions (Anderson 37-46). Tim Edensor further elaborates on the ways national identity is performed in everyday life and through popular culture, including film (Edensor 1-35). For Edensor, “national identity (...) is dynamic and dialogic” (17). Bollywood, being India’s most influential film industry, has historically played a crucial role in reinforcing and challenging nationalist ideologies. Bollywood films construct and mediate these imagined communities by visualising the nation as a unified cultural entity, often through depictions of cross-border relationships and conflict resolution. Partha Chatterjee, in his critique of nationalism, argues that cultural nationalism often operates within a dual framework of modernity and tradition, where cinema serves as a tool for both reinforcement and subversion of state ideologies (Chatterjee 116-134).

Alternative Border Narratives in Bollywood

The cinematic representation of the India-Pakistan border has evolved over the decades, reflecting shifting socio-political

attitudes. Early Bollywood war films such as *Border* (1997) and *LOC Kargil* (2003) embraced jingoistic narratives, reinforcing a rigid binary of “self” (India) versus “other” (Pakistan). These films often depicted Pakistani characters through a militarised lens, emphasising conflict and hostility. However, a gradual shift towards more peace-oriented narratives has emerged, offering a counter-discourse to nationalist rhetoric. Films such as *Main Hoon Na* (2004) and *Bajrangi Bhaijaan* (2015) propose humanised perspectives of cross-border relations, challenging the traditional enemy trope and emphasising shared cultural heritage (Dudrah15-27). The role of *Veer-Zaara* in this cinematic transition is significant. “The cross-border story of love,” as Ayesha Ali Shan has pointed out, “between a Pakistani and an Indian and the resistance to their togetherness has been projected in this all-time Saga” (32). Unlike its predecessors, the film eschews militaristic nationalism in favour of an emotional and cultural rapprochement. Prior scholarship on *Veer-Zaara* has examined its unique portrayal of Indo-Pak relations. Banerjee argues that the film constructs a “borderless” love story that subverts conventional cinematic nationalism by emphasising human connections over political divisions (Banerjee 243-245). Similarly, the film’s spatial representation of the border using shared cultural markers like Punjab’s landscapes, language, and music creates a liminal space that blurs the distinctions between India and Pakistan. Thus, Ayesha Ali Shan notes that “it can be assessed that Bollywood films possess a culture of presenting the image of Pakistan and the Muslim characters from a neutral context, sometimes with some positive attitudes as implied by movies like *Main Hoon Na* and *Veer-Zaara*.” (32)

The study of borders in cinema aligns with critical geopolitics, which examines how popular culture constructs and

negotiates territorial identities. Shubhi Misra's analysis of borders in cinema suggests that films serve as both reinforcement and subversion of geopolitical ideologies (Misra 39-40). She further states that "Films at times deconstruct the idea and concept of borders, but at the same time, they also try to bring out the significance of borders and related geopolitics through visual imagery and imagination." (40) The portrayal of the India-Pakistan border in *Veer-Zaara* moves away from militarisation towards a narrative of reconciliation, aligning with Benedict Anderson's argument that nations are not static entities but fluid constructs that can be reshaped through cultural discourse (Anderson 37-46). Besides, the role of gender in shaping these narratives is crucial. Lal examines how the representation of women in border narratives often serves as a metaphor for the nation itself, with female characters symbolising the vulnerability or strength of the homeland (Lal 113-115). In *Veer-Zaara*, Zaara's journey across the border represents not just an individual love story but a broader metaphor for the possibility of cross-border harmony. The film's subversion of conventional nationalist rhetoric through its depiction of female agency contributes to a larger discourse on peace-building in South Asian cinema.

Deconstructing the Border in *Veer-Zaara*

Veer-Zaara recounts the love story of an Indian man and a Pakistani woman who are torn apart by personal and political challenges. The narrative unfolds mainly through flashbacks from a prison cell in Lahore, Pakistan, where Veer is wrongfully imprisoned. A young lawyer, Saamiya Siddiqui (played by Rani Mukerji), is appointed by the Human Rights Commission in Pakistan to represent Veer. As they develop a bond, Veer opens up about his past. Veer Pratap Singh (Shah Rukh Khan), a helicopter

squadron leader in the Indian Air Force, works along the India-Pakistan border. During a rescue mission in the mountains, he saves Zaara Hayaat Khan (played by Preity Zinta), a Pakistani woman travelling alone to fulfill her elderly nanny Bebe's (Zohra Sehgal) final wish. Bebe, a Sikh woman who has lived in Pakistan since Partition, wants her ashes to be scattered at a sacred site in Punjab, India. Seeing that Zaara is travelling alone, Veer offers to accompany her. Along the way, he invites her to his village, where she meets his family and experiences the warmth of rural Punjab. There, Veer and Zaara develop a deep connection that turns into love. However, Zaara goes back to Pakistan for her arranged marriage. Later, she realises she truly loves Veer. Hoping to see her again, Veer travels to Pakistan. But Razaa, Zaara's fiancé, stands in their way. Razaa falsely claims Veer is an Indian spy, which leads to his arrest. Veer stays silent to protect Zaara's name and spends 22 years in prison. A young lawyer named Saamiya works hard to reopen his case. After many brawls, she was able to prove his innocence. At the end, Veer and Zaara reunite after ages and return to India together. It shows that true love can survive anything, even time and distance.

The border between India and Pakistan is often viewed as a firm line drawn by decades of political and national tension. Yet *Veer-Zaara* questions this perception by presenting the border as a space of shared memories and emotions. The depiction of the rural landscape of Punjab in the film emphasises a cultural continuity that softens the divide between the two nations. As Shuri Mariasih Gietty Tambunan has observed, "The film depicted Pakistan's landscapes not through any visualisation but through the Pakistani character's words and description." (48) While Indian Punjab is portrayed with vivid realism, Pakistan appears through recollections and feelings which evoke familiarity rather than

difference. The Wagah Border, which is often marked by displays of nationalism and military pride, becomes a site of reunion and emotional healing in the film. This transformation suggests that human connections can transcend political boundaries. Through its narrative and imagery, *Veer-Zaara* invites viewers to see the border not as a symbol of division but as a reminder of the deep cultural and historical ties that unite the two countries.

Beyond spatial representation, engagement of the film with gender as a mediator of cross-border tensions is pivotal in dismantling nationalist binaries. Zaara, the Pakistani protagonist, serves as both a literal and symbolic figure. Her journey from Pakistan to India and her eventual entrapment within patriarchal and nationalist constraints mirror the suppression of cross-border agency. Her character embodies the complex dynamics of cultural and political belonging, wherein women are often depicted as bearers of national honour and, consequently, as subjects of control (Lal 115-117). Saamiya, the female lawyer who advocates for Veer's release, further subverts traditional power structures by challenging both patriarchal and nationalist hegemonies. In her role as a defender of justice, she represents a modernised, gendered intervention in state-driven narratives of conflict, reinforcing the potential for peace-building through feminist agency (Shan31-32). Bollywood frequently employs romance as a reconciliatory tool, and *Veer-Zaara* follows this tradition by presenting love as a force that transcends territorial divisions. However, unlike conventional love stories that reinforce national loyalty, this film redefines romantic longing as a means of questioning the very legitimacy of the border itself. Through Zaara and Saamiya, *Veer-Zaara* critiques the rigid nationalism that often denies individual agency, demonstrating that women in cross-border narratives are not

merely passive symbols but active agents of mediation and reconciliation.

The film's emotional and musical strategies further destabilise nationalist discourse by invoking spiritual and cultural motifs that transcend state-defined identities. The song *Aisa Desh Hai Mera* explicitly blurs the distinction between India and Pakistan, lyrically and visually depicting a common Punjabi ethos that defies geopolitical separation. As Rajinder Dudrah notes, "Often, when Veer and Zaara are together in the same frame, the music is neither signalled as Indian or Pakistani but a mixture, a blend of the two signifiers being evoked as one through the audio and visual registers." (23) The inclusion of Sufi and Sikh spiritual elements reinforces an ideology of unity, drawing from a historical tradition that predates Partition and emphasising the futility of contemporary hostilities (Dudrah23). The use of music as an emotional register allows *Veer-Zaara* to construct an effective counter-narrative, where sentiment and cultural memory override nationalist antagonism. Emotional storytelling, particularly through Veer's unjust imprisonment and Zaara's sacrifices, subverts the state-driven hostility that typically defines Indo-Pak relations in Bollywood cinema. *Veer-Zaara*, by prioritising human emotions over political animosities, aligns itself with a tradition of alternative border narratives that seek to humanise rather than demonise the "other". Ultimately, the film offers a vision of reconciliation through a shared history of cultural intimacy and the enduring power of love, standing as a cinematic testament to the idea that borders, both physical and ideological, can be overcome through human connection.

At the climax of *Veer-Zaara*, there is a deeply moving courtroom scene where Veer Pratap Singh recites a poem titled

Prisoner No. 786. This poem holds profound significance as it emphasises the themes of India-Pakistan unity, shared heritage, and the deep cultural connections between the two nations. When the judge allows Veer to speak, he uses this moment to express his thoughts on his imprisonment, his perception of the world from behind bars, and the idea that, despite political divisions, the people on both sides of the border are not so different.

“I, prisoner number 786, look outside through these
bars of my prison cell
See the days, months, years turn into decades.
From this earth, I can smell the fragrance of my
father's fields.
This sunlight makes me remember my mother's
chilled lassi.
This rainfall brings me the movement of the swings
during the monsoon.
This winter brings me back the memories of the fire
on the Lodi night.
They tell me that this is not your country.
Then why does it seem like mine?
They tell me that I am not like them.
Then why do they seem like me? (...)” (*Veer-
Zaara*)

Through poetic verses, Veer reflects on his life in Pakistan and draws parallels with his homeland in India. He speaks of the familiar scents, weather, and emotions that transcend national boundaries, challenging the notion that the two countries are fundamentally different. He subtly critiques those who believe in rigid divisions, stating that everything—from the land to the people—feels the same to him. The poem also highlights the

influence of two women who shape Veer's life. One is Saamiya, the lawyer who fights with courage and conviction to secure his freedom. The other is Zaara, the woman he loves, who sacrifices her own life in Pakistan to dedicate herself to his village in India. When Veer recites his poem, his voice and words carry such deep emotion that they move everyone present in the courtroom, including the judge. The scene ends with a heartfelt standing ovation, capturing the power of love, sacrifice, and human connection. It reminds us that while borders may divide nations, they can never break the emotional bonds and shared histories that unite people across them.

The political narrative that defines the India–Pakistan border has long been dominated by the language of conflict. It is marked by territorial disputes, military tensions, and deeply rooted nationalist rhetoric. This discourse consistently portrays the neighbouring country as an opponent rather than a partner in dialogue. However, *Veer-Zaara* presents a counterpoint to this statist narrative. It shifts the focus from the politics of division to the human stories that transcend borders. Instead of reinforcing hostility, the film advocates for a people-centric understanding of Indo-Pak relations, where shared cultural traditions, familial bonds, and personal sacrifices hold more significance than political rivalries. The film's portrayal of Veer, an Indian Air Force officer who willingly sacrifices his identity and freedom for love, and Zaara, a Pakistani woman who chooses human relationships over nationalist allegiances, serves as a direct critique of state-driven narratives that rigidly define patriotism in exclusionary terms (Lal 115-117). The repeated visual and thematic emphasis on cultural similarity rather than difference, depicted through shared traditions, language, and familial values, further cements the film's advocacy for people-to-people diplomacy as a viable path toward

reconciliation. By rejecting the idea of a monolithic enemy and replacing it with complex, empathetic individuals on both sides of the border, *Veer-Zaara* subverts the conventional nationalist binary of “self” versus “other” (Tambunan 44-59).

At the heart of *Veer-Zaara* is the idea that cross-border love can function as a symbol of hope, challenging nationalist militarism by placing personal relationships above political conflicts. The film’s narrative arc, which follows Veer’s self-imposed incarceration in Pakistan for 22 years, underscores how individual sacrifices often carry deeper political significance, particularly in the context of rigidly divided nations. As Chatterjee argues, nationalism is often constructed through rigid ideological frameworks, but it is in the realm of the personal that these structures can be dismantled (Chatterjee 95-115). Veer’s decision to resign from the Indian Air Force has a deep symbolic meaning. It epitomizes a conscious move away from militaristic nationalism toward a more human-centered sense of solidarity. Conventional war films such as *Border* (1997) or *LOC Kargil* (2003) glorify military service as the highest form of patriotism. Whereas *Veer-Zaara* redefines heroism as the courage to rise above national boundaries through love and selfless action. As Ayesha Ali Shan observed, “*Veer-Zaara* showed a cross-line heartfelt story focusing on penance, love, and mankind, presenting a positive image of the two nations”. This reversal of traditional ideals reflects a broader shift in Bollywood’s portrayal of cross-border relations. Similar to films like *Bajrangi Baijaan* (2015), which use personal relationships to challenge entrenched hostilities (Dudrah15-27), *Veer-Zaara* questions the nationalist narrative that views India–Pakistan relations solely through the lens of conflict. Instead, it offers a vision grounded in empathy, cultural continuity, and shared humanity. The message of the film extends beyond its story

to contribute meaningfully to peace studies and cultural diplomacy. By presenting love as a bridge across divisions, the film opens a new discourse for younger audiences, one that values reconciliation over rivalry. The popularity of the film in both India and Pakistan demonstrates the unique ability of cinema to transcend ideological divides and foster understanding. In a region where political negotiations often falter, *Veer-Zaara* stands as a reminder that art can imagine alternative futures where borders are not barriers but meeting points of shared human experience.

Conclusion

In conclusion, thus we can say, Veer-Zaarais a powerful cinematic work for contesting conventional border narratives by turning the focus from hostility to human connection. It is not like other so-called mainstream Bollywood films that reinforce nationalist divisions. Rather, it portrays India–Pakistan relations through shared culture and emotion instead of politics and conflict. Here, the film presents rural Punjab as a common cultural space as a counter-narrative that rejects militaristic nationalism. It values personal bonds over state-driven enmity. The film also breaks away from the usual portrayal of Pakistan as an adversary. By depicting humane and relatable characters on both sides of the border, it portrays Pakistan as part of the same cultural and emotional continuum as India. Its ability to inspire empathy for people across the divide creates an alternative narrative that transcends rigid territorial nationalism. It shows shared history and identity. Thus, *Veer-Zaara* redefines Indo–Pak relations through its emotionally rich storytelling and visual depiction of a “borderless” Punjab. It suggests that love and sacrifice endure far beyond the reach of political conflict. The film also shows the broader role of Bollywood in shaping cross-border perceptions and peace-building

efforts. Bollywood, being one of India's most powerful cultural exports, holds immense potential in shifting the dominant narrative on Indo-Pak relations from conflict to cooperation. However, the need for more nuanced film narratives that go beyond state propaganda remains crucial. While Bollywood has historically oscillated between hyper-nationalistic war films and peace-oriented romances, there is still a gap in truly complex portrayals of border issues that acknowledge the socio-political realities while also advocating for reconciliation. Hence, Ayesha Ali Shan has rightly stated that "movies like *Veer Zara* shows a cinematic rendition of cross-border love by harmonising neighbouring countries with humanitarian efforts" (39). Future narratives must move beyond simplistic binaries of hero and villain. Instead, it should offer a more layered exploration of cross-border identities, migration, and cultural hybridity.

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